

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND FRACTURE RESISTANCE OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL GRAPHENE/POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This work reports the development of three-dimensional (3D) graphene structures, such as graphene aerogels (GAs), graphene woven fabrics (GWFs) and graphene foams (GFs), as interconnected fillers for polymer composites in an effort to achieve excellent mechanical properties and fracture resistance. The 3D graphene structures are aimed at totally eliminating the issue of filler dispersion using a few rational assembly techniques, such as liquid crystal based self-assembly, unidirectional freeze casting and template-directed chemical vapor deposition (CVD). The resulting 3D graphene structures are infiltrated with liquid epoxy resins followed by the thermal curing to obtain the composites. The 3D graphene/epoxy composites show concurrently improved elastic modulus, strength and fracture toughness. While the enhancements in modulus and strength of the composites are rather moderate due to the difficulties in achieving strong interfacial bonds, remarkable improvements in fracture toughness by 100 % against solid epoxy are achieved. The aligned rGO sheets, porous graphene struts, interwoven hollow graphene tubes, and high-density graphene networks facilitate unique toughening mechanisms, such as crack deflection, crack tip blunting, crack pinning and bifurcation, leading to significant energy dissipation during crack propagation giving rise to exceptional fracture resistances. Compared to GAs assembled from GO solutions, GFs and GWFs made by templated-directed CVD generally show better reinforcing effects due to the high-quality, seamlessly interconnected graphene networks. In view of such excellent reinforcing and toughening effects, the 3D graphene can also serve as interleaves to strengthen and toughen the conventional fiber reinforced composites, contributing to enhanced interlaminar fracture toughness. The excellent mechanical properties and fracture resistances render 3D graphene/epoxy composites a serious contender for emerging multifunctional applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Graphene has been touted as an ideal reinforcement for polymer composites due to its unique two-dimensional (2D) geometry with an immense specific surface area and ultrahigh in-plane modulus (~ 1 TPa), strength (~250 GPa) and fracture toughness (4 MPa m^{1/2}). [1,2] In theory, harnessing such excellent properties of graphene could yield nanocomposites with staggering mechanical and fracture properties. However, translating the excellent intrinsic properties of graphene to bulk nanocomposites is untrivial, if not completely impossible, using conventional composite fabrication technologies, which involve direct mixing of reinforcing fillers with polymer matrices in molten states or using solvents. [3] Several challenging issues impede the reinforcing effects of 2D graphene in composites. Firstly, the randomly dispersed 2D graphene sheets in the polymer matrix can be considered as discontinuous particulate reinforcements, similar to short fiber-reinforced composites. [4] The load-bearing capabilities of graphene sheets are therefore significantly affected by their lateral dimensions and those with small sizes are generally poor load bearers in the composites. Secondly, the uniform dispersion of graphene sheets in the matrix is problematic particularly at a high filler loading. This issue arises from the drastically increased viscosity of polymers beyond processing capabilities due to the enormous interfacial volume associated with the extremely large surface area of graphene. [5] Thirdly, controlling the alignment of graphene sheets along the loading direction is not straightforward as they tend to randomly orient and be easily folded and wrinkled in the matrix when conventional processing techniques are performed. [6] Such random orientations and defects further diminish the reinforcing effects as the mechanical

properties of graphene in the thickness direction are much inferior to those along the plane. Owing to the abovementioned issues, the overall mechanical properties, including modulus, strength, and fracture toughness of the composites with graphene reinforcements are often far below the estimates based on the rule of mixtures equation. The elastic modulus of composites depends on the aspect ratio and orientation of graphene [7]. The exceptionally high modulus of graphene (1 TPa) has not been fully exploited due to the low aspect ratio and lack of alignment. Compared to the modulus, the strength and fracture toughness are more sensitive to the presence of defects and interfacial adhesion.[8] As such, the improvements in strength and fracture toughness highly depend on the interfacial properties and uniform dispersion of graphene, in addition to the alignment and high aspect ratio of fillers. Unfortunately, uniform dispersion at a few wt% graphene sheets are already extremely difficult to achieve using conventional techniques. The agglomerated fillers can act as stress concentrators, and consequently, the strength and fracture toughness of composites at high filler loadings are even lower than the pure polymer matrices.[5]

To tackle the above challenges and better translate the excellent mechanical properties of graphene into composites, the 2D building blocks of graphene need to be rationally assembled such that their orientations, dispersions, and interconnections in polymer matrices are fully controllable. In this work, we report several rationally assembled three-dimensional (3D) graphene structures, such as graphene aerogels (GAs), graphene woven fabrics (GWFs) and graphene foams (GFs), as fillers for polymer composites. These 3D graphene structures facilitated simultaneous uniform dispersion, inherent interconnection, controllable orientation and high filler contents of graphene when infiltrated with a polymer matrix. The resulting nanocomposites deliver simultaneously high stiffness, strength and excellent fracture resistance, providing a promising route for future development of graphene composites for structural and multifunctional applications.

2 3D GRAPHENE STRUCTURES AND THEIR POLYMER COMPOSITES

The key strategy we have adopted to eliminate the issue of dispersion is to first assemble 2D graphene sheets into well-defined, porous 3D architectures, which serve as pre-dispersed 3D fillers for subsequent infiltration of liquid epoxy resins followed by thermal curing. To obtain 3D graphene structures, two approaches were used, namely, self-assembly and template-directed assembly. The self-assembly technique exploited the unique liquid crystal (LC) phases of graphene oxide (GO) in aqueous solutions to induce self-alignment of GO sheets. The template-directed assembly utilized dynamic ice crystals and 3D metal foams or meshes as templates to direct the assembly of 2D GO or the growth graphene sheets. Using these techniques, 3D graphene structures such as GAs, GFs, and GWFs with unique microstructures were obtained. After infiltrating epoxy resins into the pores of 3D graphene structures followed by curing, nanocomposites containing well-dispersed, inherently interconnected and preferably oriented graphene were obtained.

2.1 Self-aligned GAs made by self-assembly of GO LC

The LC nature of anisotropic GO facilitates the spontaneous development of nematic order in aqueous solutions [9]. Such a process was driven by entropy due to the excluded volume effect without the need of external stimulations.[10,11] Upon solvent removal, GO sheets self-assembled into bulk structures with microscopic orders inherited from the nematic phases [12] where long-range alignments were achieved by manipulating the morphologies of 2D LCs, especially when GO sheets of ultralarge sizes and high wt% were used. The ultralarge GO sheets could self-assemble into a layered structure in an aqueous solution according to the excluded volume theory [9]. Such a characteristic of self-alignment was exploited to fabricate GAs using a one-step reduction and sol-gel process (Figure 1a) [13]. The ultralarge GO sheets with a mean area of $\sim 200 \mu\text{m}^2$ (Figure 1b) were reduced by hydroiodic acid (HI), followed by sol-gel process and freeze-drying. The GAs made from high-concentration GO dispersion (2 mg mL^{-1}) featured a layered structure consisting of horizontally aligned rGO sheets with minor, vertically oriented sheets connecting the aligned layers (Figures 1c and d). This is in stark contrast with those GAs made from low concentration GO dispersions or small-size GO sheets, which showed mostly random distribution. The self-alignment of ultralarge GO sheets was an entropy-driven process to minimize the excluded volume, and the steric hindrance between the highly concentrated GO sheets

prevented re-agglomeration of GO sheets during the sol-gel process. These aligned GA structure remained intact even after infiltration with liquid epoxy resin, yielding solid composites having interconnected graphene sheets.

Figure 1. (a) Fabrication of aligned GAs by self-assembly of GO LCs; scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of (b) GO sheets; (c) GAs with aligned rGO walls; and (d) rGO layers at a higher magnification.[13]

2.2 Unidirectional GAs made by unidirectional freeze casting

Dynamic ice templating, also known as directional freeze casting, is a technique that uses growing ice crystals as templates to assemble colloidal particles in aqueous solutions into a 3D macroscopic network with a controlled morphology. The uniform GO aqueous dispersions were poured into a mold and placed on the copper container immersed in liquid nitrogen (Figure 2a). The ice crystals grew from the bottom to top along the temperature gradient, expelling the solid GO sheets between ice lamellae (Figure 2b). Upon removal of ice crystals by freeze drying and thermal reduction, unidirectional GAs (UGAs) with vertically aligned pores surrounded by rGO walls were obtained (Figure 2b) [14]. The precise control of structural features, such as the density, porosity and degree of alignment, depended on two important parameters, including the lateral dimensions of GO sheets and the GO concentrations. Ultralarge GO (ULGO) sheets with a mean size of $1596 \mu\text{m}^2$ led to much better alignments (Figures 2c-d) than small-size GO (SGO) with a mean size of $1.1 \mu\text{m}^2$ (Figures 2e-f).[15] With increasing GO concentration, the UGAs with ultralarge GO sheets showed better aligned and thicker pore walls. In addition, higher GO concentrations also gave rise to higher densities of UGAs, contributing to higher filler contents of the composites.

Figure 2. (a) Schematics of the apparatus used for freeze-casting; (b) schematics of freeze-casting and freeze-drying processes to obtain UGAs; SEM images of UGAs made from (c-d) ULGO and (e-f) SGO sheets. (c) and (e) are the top views, and (d) and (f) are the side views.[15]

2.3 GFs and GWFs made by template-directed chemical vapor deposition (CVD)

2D graphene can be grown on metal substrates using the CVD technique [16]. The CVD method was able to produce mono- or few-layer graphene with higher qualities and larger lateral dimensions [17] than the solution-based exfoliation of GO. In addition, the structures of interconnected graphene networks can be tailored using templates with 3D morphologies.

Templates such as Ni foams and meshes were used as substrates for CVD to grow 3D structures from 2D graphene. 3D GFs were grown on Ni foam templates using methane gas (CH_4) as the carbon source at 1000 °C to obtain Ni-graphene foams (Figure 3a). After coating a protective poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) layer, the Ni foam was etched out using a mixture of FeCl_3 and HCl. The freestanding GF was finally obtained by dissolving PMMA in hot acetone, which is highly porous (Figure 3b) with an extremely low density of $\sim 1.3 \text{ mg/cm}^3$ and interconnected graphene struts consisting of mono- to few-layer graphene walls.[18] A porous GF/epoxy nanocomposite with a pore volume of $\sim 19 \text{ vol } \%$ was obtained by infiltrating epoxy resin before etching the Ni foam (Figure 3c) [18]. Alternatively, the epoxy resin was directly infiltrated into the freestanding GF, resulting in a solid nanocomposite with dense graphene struts [19].

In addition to Ni foams, Ni meshes with interwoven structures also served as templates to produce GWFs [20]. The CVD process was essentially the same as that for GFs, and the freestanding GWF synthesized thereby was light-weight and flexible containing well-defined orthogonally interweaved graphene tubes [20], as shown in Figure 3d. The nanocomposite was made by infiltrating polymer into the Ni-GWF structure, followed by etching the Ni meshes [20]. Compared to cellular GFs, the most distinctive feature of planar GWF is its well-defined mesh structure consisting of orthogonal, hollow graphene tubes. The densities of GFs and GWFs were readily controlled by methane concentrations [18]. Higher methane concentrations yielded thicker graphene sheets and thus higher densities of GFs and GWFs, which in turn led to higher graphene loadings in the composites.

The maximum graphene content obtained in nanocomposites using common 3D GFs or GWFs was less than 1 wt % due to the intrinsically large pores in the templates and thin layers of graphene. Such low loadings of graphene seriously limit the overall mechanical and functional performance of nanocomposites. Therefore, high-density GFs are highly desired to increase the overall filler loadings. Although compressing freestanding GFs was a straightforward way to increase their densities [21], the 3D cellular structures were collapsed completely under compression, leading to disappearance of pores and fragmented 3D networks unable to process to incorporate polymers. Alternatively, direct growth of graphene on high-density 3D templates was carried out [19]. Several layers of commercial Ni foams

were stacked and compressed to a multilayer Ni web with significantly reduced pore sizes, serving as the template to grow a multilayer graphene web (MGW) with an ultrahigh density ten times that of the common GF [19]. Unlike the isotropic GF structure, the MGW consisted of in-plane oriented graphene struts densely packed along the thickness direction (Figure 3e). The ultrahigh-density MGW was infiltrated with epoxy resins, giving rise to a high graphene content of 8.3 wt % in the final composites [19].

Figure 3. (a) Schematics of the fabrication of GF by the template-directed CVD; SEM images of (b) GF [18], (c) porous GF/epoxy composite [18], (d) GWF [20] and (e) MGW [19].

3 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND FRACTURE RESISTANCES

3.1 Elastic moduli of 3D graphene/polymer composites

The enhancement in elastic modulus, ΔE , of 3D graphene/epoxy composites was assessed by plotting $\Delta E = E - E_m$ against the graphene content, where E is the elastic modulus of composites and E_m is the modulus of matrix, as shown in Figure 2a. The moduli of the composites containing GAs and UGAs were measured along the alignment direction. Compared to dispersed rGO with self-alignment in the polyurethane (PU) matrix (Figure 2b, i) [22], these composites with interconnected graphene structures exhibited higher enhancements. At a relatively low graphene content, the modulus along the alignment direction even approached the theoretical values predicted by the Halpin-Tsai model:[22,23]

$$E_{\parallel} = \left[\frac{1+2/3\alpha\eta_{\parallel}V_f}{1-\eta_{\parallel}V_f} \right] E_m, \text{ where } \eta_{\parallel} = \frac{E_f/E_m-1}{E_f/E_m+2/3\alpha}. \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), E_f and E_m are the Young's moduli of rGO (250 GPa) [24] and epoxy (2.5 GPa), V_f is the filler content and α is the aspect ratio of rGO sheets. Such enhancements were attributed to several important factors, including the high aspect ratios of rGO sheets, their excellent alignments and the interconnected GA and UGA structures (Figure 2b, ii). With increasing graphene content, the enhancement in modulus became saturated and deviated from the theoretical predictions, due probably to increasing thicknesses of the rGO walls. A thicker rGO wall contained more rGO layers, which slipped against each other when loaded and thus gave rise to lower load carrying capabilities.

The CVD-grown graphene exhibited a higher intrinsic modulus of up to 500 GPa than rGO sheets (250 GPa) due to its high-quality crystal structures [25–27]. Highly aligned CVD-grown graphene/polycarbonate (PC) composites made by layer stacking (Figure 2b, iv) showed impressive modulus enhancements at ultralow graphene contents, approaching the theoretical limit predicted by the simple rule of mixtures [28]. However, such a layer stacking strategy is only applicable to thermoplastic matrices as repetitive hot pressings are required. In comparison, the porous 3D GFs and GWFs allowed easy infiltration of both molten thermoplastics and liquid thermoset resins. Both the GF/epoxy [18] and GWF/epoxy [20] composites presented higher enhancements in modulus than the 3D GA and UGA counterparts. In particular, the GF/epoxy composites showed an enhancement approaching the upper limit predicted by the rule of mixtures [18], similar to the aligned graphene/PC composites. This remarkable outcome arose from the seamlessly interconnected graphene networks spanning the whole

dimensions of the composite, allowing the loads to be carried mainly by the GF structure. With increasing graphene content, the moduli slightly decreased relative to the upper limit prediction because of the interlayer slippage as the thickness of graphene layers increased.

Figure 4. (a) Comparison of moduli of 3D graphene/epoxy composites (ii. GA/epoxy [13]; iii. UGA/epoxy [15]; v. GF/epoxy [18]; vi. GWF/epoxy [20]) with those of dispersed rGO (i. aligned rGO/PU [22]) and aligned CVD-grown graphene/polymer composites (iv. Graphene/PC [28]). The dash lines are the predictions based on the Halpin-Tsai model with various aspect ratios, α , and the blue and red solid lines are the predictions from the rule of mixtures. (b) Schematics and cross-sectional SEM images of graphene/polymer composites with different morphologies corresponding to those in (a): i. aligned rGO/PU composites [22]; ii and iii. GA and UGA/epoxy composites [13,15]; iv. CVD-grown graphene/PC composites [28]; and v. 3D GF/epoxy composites [18].

3.2 Strengths of 3D graphene/polymer composites

For 3D graphene/epoxy composites, the strengths were not compromised by the improved elastic moduli, as shown in Figure 5a. For GAs and UGAs, the improvements in flexural strength were rather moderate with only about 10 % higher than solid epoxy when ULGO sheets were used. [13,15] Compared to the 3D graphene structure assembled with rGO sheets, GFs and GWFs grown by CVD led to higher enhancements in strength of composites. Although the GWF/epoxy composites showed lower absolute values due to their hollow tubes, the enhancement in tensile strength was higher at 28 % [20]. A maximum strength was obtained with 0.2 wt% GFs, which is 38 % higher than solid epoxy [18].

Several factors are deemed critical for the concurrently improved strength and modulus. Firstly, the excellent dispersion arising from the predefined 3D graphene structures eliminate the adverse stress concentrations which are common for randomly dispersed nanofillers [5]. Secondly, the large lateral dimensions and high aspect ratios of graphene ensures effective load transfer. For the UGA made from small-size GO sheets with a mean area of $1.1 \mu\text{m}^2$, the flexural strength of the composites decreased slightly while the modulus increased, in contrast to both enhanced strength and modulus of the UGA composites made from ULGO with a mean area of $1596 \mu\text{m}^2$. The same can also be explained by the critical size of $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ required for an effective stress transfer between graphene and the polymer matrix according to the shear lag theory [4]. Ideally, a graphene size larger than 10 times the critical value, *i.e.* $\sim 30 \mu\text{m}$, is required for most effective reinforcement. As such, large-size rGO sheets with high aspect ratios are preferred for efficient strengthening. Thirdly, the interconnected high-quality graphene networks contribute to improved strengths. Both GFs and GWFs prepared by CVD had much higher quality graphene networks than GAs and UGAs, offering higher reinforcing efficiencies. It is also noted that the GWFs/epoxy composites even showed higher elongations before fracture than the neat epoxy, while other composites exhibited somewhat constant or reduced fracture strains (Figure 5a, dashed lines). The orthogonally aligned graphene tubes in GWFs functioned as strong and tough fibers, increasing the fracture strains when loaded in these two directions [20].

It should be noted that the improvements in composite strength were still lower than the predictions

from the rule of mixtures. This can be understood from the fact that neither rGO nor CVD-grown graphene were able to form strong interfacial bonds with the epoxy matrix due to the lack of reactive functional groups on their surfaces [13,15,18,20]. The interfacial bond strength between the pristine graphene and polymer matrix was determined to be only ~1 MPa according to the Raman spectroscopy mapping [4]. This value is much lower than the typical interfacial bond strengths, 20–40 MPa, for carbon fiber/polymer interfaces. This means that functionalization of rGO or CVD-grown graphene is required to further improve the strengths of composites. Nevertheless, a tradeoff must be made between the interfacial bond strength and the intrinsic strength of graphene as chemical functionalization would inevitably lower the strength of graphene through defect creation.

Figure 5. Ashby plots of (a) strength against modulus and (b) fracture toughness against modulus of 3D graphene/epoxy composites.

3.3 Fracture toughness

Fracture resistance is more relevant to and crucial for practical engineering applications than strength. Similar to the strength, the fracture toughness is sensitive to agglomeration of nanofillers which allows easy propagation of cracks. Figure 5b presents that the 3D graphene structures had improved fracture toughness of composites with increasing modulus due to their well dispersed and interconnected rGO or graphene networks. Compared to the moderate improvements in strength, the fracture toughness exhibited more significant enhancements with the addition of 3D graphene structures. Solid GA/epoxy and UGA/epoxy composites gave rise to about 60 % enhancements against solid epoxy [13,15]. Porous epoxy showed 15 to 30 % higher fracture toughness values than their solid counterparts, due to the additional toughening mechanisms brought by the well dispersed and oriented pores [18,20]. GFs and GWFs yielded even higher fracture toughness of composites than the GA and UGA counterparts, achieving remarkable 70 to 80 % enhancements against solid epoxy [18,20].

The interconnected cellular graphene structures imparted unique toughening mechanisms responsible for the highly improved fracture toughness of epoxy composites (Figure 6). GA/epoxy solid composites showed rough, stair-like fracture surfaces when cracks were deflected by aligned GO layers (Figure 6b, i), leading to huge dissipation of energy and thus improved fracture toughness of about 60 %.[13] Similarly, UGAs effectively blunted and deflected the crack tips along the interfaces between rGO and epoxy, as indicated by the rough fracture surfaces with smooth epoxy regions roughly 20 to 30 μm in size separated by the rGO networks (Figure 6b, ii) [15]. In comparison, the solid GF/epoxy composite with a similar graphene content showed a relatively smooth fracture surface with many tails along the crack propagation direction (Figure 6b, iii), indicating a crack pinning mechanism by the solid graphene struts.[19]

Interestingly, the porous GF/epoxy structure had a higher resistance to fracture than the solid counterparts, as evidenced by the rough fracture surface with protruding blocks separated by triangular-shaped pores (Figure 6b, iv).[18] These pores offered additional toughening mechanisms by effectively deflecting the crack path, leading to 70 % enhancement in fracture toughness against the solid

epoxy.[18] To maximize the effect of pores, porous GWFs/epoxy composites with orthogonal hollow graphene tubes were placed such that the crack propagated along the direction 45° to the orthogonal direction. The hollow graphene tubes (Figure 6b, v) could precisely deflect the crack away from the plane of maximum stress to that of minimum stress, requiring much higher energies for the cracks to propagate.[20] The density of graphene networks within the epoxy matrix was further increased using high-density MGWs as fillers.[19] The exceptionally high graphene content of 8.3 wt % improved the fracture toughness of composites by well over 100 % (Figure 6a). The fracture surface was very rough with multiplane facets as the cracks were twisted by the high-density graphene network (Figure 6b, vi), contributing to significant energy dissipation during crack propagation.

Figure 6. (a) Fracture toughness of MGW/epoxy composites with high filler contents of up to 8.3 wt %; (b) SEM images of the fracture surfaces of 3D graphene/epoxy composites: (i) GA/epoxy [13]; (ii) UGA/epoxy (scale bar: 100 μm) [15]; (iii) solid GF/epoxy [19]; (iv) porous GF/epoxy [18]; (v) GWF/epoxy [20]; and (vi) MGW/epoxy composites [19].

4 CONCLUSIONS

The simultaneous improvements in elastic modulus, strength and fracture resistance were achieved in graphene/epoxy nanocomposites using 3D graphene structures as pre-dispersed fillers. The rational assembly techniques enabled controllable dispersion, alignment and filler content of graphene in the epoxy matrix. As the moduli of 3D graphene/epoxy composites increased with increasing graphene content, the strengths and fracture toughness concurrently enhanced due to the well dispersed rGO or graphene sheets in the epoxy matrix. The improvements in strength were rather moderate, with 10 to 40 % enhancements against the neat epoxy. This observation arose mainly from the lack of interfacial chemical bonds between graphene and epoxy. In contrast, the fracture toughness of composites increased remarkably with the addition of 3D graphene structures, giving rise to 60 to 100 % enhancements compared to the solid epoxy. The aligned rGO sheets, porous graphene struts, interwoven hollow graphene tubes and high-density graphene networks offered unique toughening mechanisms, such as crack deflection, crack tip blunting, crack pinning and bifurcation, leading to significant energy dissipation during crack propagation. GFs, GWFs and MGWs synthesized by templated-directed CVD generally showed better reinforcing effects than GAs and UGAs prepared from GO solutions, due mainly to the high-quality, seamlessly interconnected graphene networks in the former graphene structures.

In summary, the state-of-the-art mechanical properties of graphene composites are still far from on a par with conventional fiber reinforced composites. A major issue is the meaningful filler contents that can be achieved in graphene composites are much lower than those found in fiber reinforced composites. Using high-density 3D graphene structures [19] or 1D graphene fibers [29] similar to conventional carbon fibers as fillers can be a promising route to increase the graphene content in the composite.

Another challenge is the chemical functionalization to improve the interfacial bond strength without diminishing the intrinsic properties of graphene. Nonetheless, 3D graphene structures can serve as interleaves to further strengthen and toughen the conventional fiber reinforced composites, significantly enhancing the interlaminar fracture resistance [30]. Apart from structural reinforcements, the major advantage of 3D graphene/epoxy composites lies in their intriguing multifunctional properties, such as high electrical and thermal conductivities [14,15,19]. This means that the excellent mechanical and fracture properties studied in this work provide a solid foundation for practical multifunctional applications of 3D graphene/epoxy composites.

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